

THERMAL ENERGY STORAGE SYSTEMS

FOR ENERGY EFFICIENT BUILDINGS

DEMONSTRATION SITES

SPAIN | AUSTRIA | CYPRUS

PROJECT ID

PROJECT NAME

Thermal Energy Storage Systems for Energy Efficient Buildings. An integrated solution for residential building energy storage by solar and geothermal resources

PROJECT ACRONYM

TESSe2b

DURATION

4 years

BUDGET

€ 4.311.700

PROGRAM

EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020 RESEARCH AND INNOVATION WORK PROGRAMME 2014 - 2015

TOPIC

EeB-06-2015 - Integrated solutions of thermal energy storage for building applications

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER

680 555

EXPECTED REDUCTION IN BUILDING
ENERGY CONSUMPTION **25-30%**

THE ESTIMATED PAYBACK PERIOD
IS EXPECTED TO REACH
8-9 YEARS

CONSORTIUM

- 1 IPS, Polytechnic Institute of Setubal | PORTUGAL (**COORDINATOR**)
- 2 CRES, Center for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving | GREECE
- 3 NKUA, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens | GREECE
- 4 GEOTEAM, Geoteam Technical Office for Hydrogeology, Geothermal Energy and Environment | AUSTRIA
- 5 UOI, University of Ioannina | GREECE
- 6 SGGW, Warsaw University of Life Sciences | POLAND
- 7 RUB, Ruhr University of Bochum | GERMANY
- 8 ECOSERVEIS, Association ECOSERVEIS | SPAIN
- 9 PCM, Phase Change Material Products Ltd | UNITED KINGDOM
- 10 Z&X, Z&X Mechanical Installations Ltd | CYPRUS

TESSE2B PARTNERS

TESSE²B PROJECT

TESSe2b project develops an integrated solution for residential buildings energy storage, using solar and geothermal energy, with the purpose of correcting the mismatch that often occurs between the supply and demand of energy in residential buildings. TESSe2b designs, develops, validates and demonstrates a modular and low cost thermal storage technology based on Phase Change Material (PCM) to provide domestic hot water (DHW), space heating and cooling.

The solution integrates compact Thermal Energy Storage (TES) PCM Tanks with solar collectors and highly efficient geothermal heat pumps with enhanced PCM borehole heat exchangers (BHEs). To optimize the energetic and economic performance of the entire system, TESse2b solution is managed by an advanced energy smart self-learning control system specially developed for this application.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- Select and characterize PCMs to optimize the design and performance for high efficiency PCM TES Tanks and enhanced PCM borehole heat exchangers.
- Exploit nanotechnology to develop new nanoparticles enhanced paraffin PCM (NEPCM).
- Design, optimize and develop compact modular TES units, including a high performance Heat Exchanger (HE).
- Develop a thin film coating to protect the TES tanks HE against the salt-hydrates corrosivity.
- Develop a smart self-learning control system for efficient TESS_e2b operation and integration into a robust working prototype.
- Design an effective exploitation strategy and business plan to demonstrate the overall benefits of TESS_e2b solution.

EXPECTED RESULTS

- Reduce the buildings net energy consumption in 25-30% and its associated CO₂ emissions.
- Achieve a payback period of 8-9 years.
- Increase the share of Removable Energy Sources in the building domestic sector.
- Contribute for the electric grid flexibility.

ENVIRONMENTALLY FRIENDLY, LOW COST AND SAFE

- Reduction of the environmental impact of residential buildings.
- Contribution to meet the EU's environmental objectives.
- Capability of simple and cost effective modernization of existing buildings and integration into new buildings.

DEMONSTRATION SITES

Aiming to evaluate the system's integration into a building, a demonstration and on-site monitoring evaluation of TESSE2b solution will be held in three pilot sites to assess its impact in different climates and provide evidence about its overall technical and economic feasibility.

DEMOSITE CHARACTERISTICS

DEMOSITE	AUSTRIA	CYPRUS	SPAIN
AREA (m ²)	321	221	138
HEATING CAPACITY (kW)	13,0	26,3	12,2
COOLING CAPACITY (kW)	*	18,6	12,6
HEATING ANNUAL NEEDS (kWh/m ²)	55,1	45,3	63,9
COOLING ANNUAL NEEDS (kWh/m ²)	8,67	69,9	6,85
SOLAR COLLECTORS AREA (m ²)	13,6	23,5	23,5
HOT PCM TANKS	3	3	4
COLD PCM TANKS	*	3	3
DHW TANK	1	1	1
BOREHOLE HE N°	4	8	4
DEPTH (m)	75	90	90
TOTAL LENGTH (m)	300	720	360

* FREE-COOLING

SPAIN DEMOSITE

LOCATION

CALONGE DE SEGARRA, BARCELONA REGION

41°45'50.10''N - 1°28'53.73''E

CLIMATE

MEDITERRANEAN

BSK (KÖPPEN-GEIGER CLASSIFICATION)

DESIGN TEMPERATURES

5 °C | 28 °C

BUILDING

- FAMILY HOUSE
- 4 MEMBERS
- 138 m²
- 2 FLOORS
- GARDEN AREA

The building is an old farmhouse located in Calonge de Segarra (Barcelona region, Spain). It has an area of 138 m² equally distributed in two floors. The walls of the building are made of limestone and have a 4 cm layer of polystyrene (XPS) as thermal insulation. The estimated annual energy demand of the building is 63,9 kWh/(m²year) for heating and 6,85 kWh/(m²year) for cooling. The house has an energy efficiency rating of F according with the Spain Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) regulation. The building annual energy demand estimated, for the reference envelop defined by the EPC regulation, is 56,83 kWh/(m²year) for heating and 4,23 kWh/(m²year) for cooling.

SYSTEM LAYOUT

In Spain's demosite, the system was designed as a set of PCM storage tanks coupled with a geothermal heat pump, flat solar collectors and fan coils inside the house. The thermal energy storage PCM tanks stores energy at three different levels. The Cold storage tanks for residential space cooling, the Hot storage tanks for residential space heating and a TES tank to deliverable DHW.

The PCM storage tank for DWH supply is linked directly to the solar loop and the heat pump. An electric water heater is installed in series after the PCM hot water tank as a backup for the production of hot water. The solar loop has a heat dissipater for safety reasons.

A buffer tank with six connections couples the fan coils circuit of the house, the three Hot PCM tanks, the three Cold PCM tanks and the heat pump. The geothermal system has four boreholes, two regular and two enhanced with PCM. More than 50 temperature sensors, nine humidity sensors and six flow meters are installed to control and monitor the system operation. The control and monitoring data are centralized in a custom-made electronic system which processes more than 100 variables per second.

SPAIN DEMOSITE SYSTEM LAYOUT

AUSTRIA DEMOSITE

LOCATION

KAPFENBERG, GRAZ REGION
47°26'30.4"N - 15°18'02.56"E

CLIMATE

CONTINENTAL
DFB (KÖPPEN-GEIGER CLASSIFICATION)

DESIGN TEMPERATURES

-5 °C | 24 °C

BUILDING

- FAMILY HOUSE
- 4 MEMBERS
- 321 m²
- 1 FLOOR
- GARDEN AREA

The building is a residential house located in Kapfenberg (Graz region, Austria). It has one floor with a total area of 321 m². It was built in 2003, the thermal insulation was retrofitted in 2010 installing a 14-18 cm layer of polystyrene (EPS). The estimated annual energy demand of the building for heating is 55,1 kWh/(m²year) and 8,67 kWh/(m²year) for cooling. The house has an energy efficiency rating of D according with the Austria Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) regulation. The building annual energy demand estimated for the reference envelop defined by the EPC regulation is 44,35 kWh/(m²year) for heating and 10,12 kWh/(m²year) for cooling.

SYSTEM LAYOUT

In Austria's demosite, the system has four hot PCM storage tanks coupled with a geothermal heat pump, vacuum tube solar collectors and a indoor heating system (low temperature radiator and radiant floor heating). The PCM tanks stores energy at two levels, one for residential space heating and another at high level to provide DHW. The PCM storage tank for delivering DWH is linked directly to the solar loop and the heat pump. An electric water heater is installed in series after the PCM hot water tank as a backup for the production of hot water.

A buffer tank with four connections couples the indoor circuit, the heat pump and the Hot PCM tanks. One of the heating tanks is not in operation. The geothermal system has four boreholes, two of them enhanced with PCM.

More than 50 temperature sensors, 12 humidity sensors and 12 heat meters are installed to monitoring and control the system operation. The control and monitoring data are centralized in a custom-made electronic system which processes more than 100 variables per second.

AUSTRIA DEMOSITE SYSTEM LAYOUT

CYPRUS DEMOSITE

LOCATION

MILIOU VILLAGE, PAFOS REGION
34°55'58.59"N - 32°27'57.37"E

CLIMATE

MEDITERRANEAN,
CSA (KÖPPEN-GEIGER CLASSIFICATION)

DESIGN TEMPERATURES

7 °C | 30 °C

BUILDING

- FAMILY HOUSE
- 4 MEMBERS
- 221 m²
- 2 FLOORS
- GARDEN AREA

The building is located in Meliou (Pafos region), Cyprus. It is a residential house with an area of 221 m² distributed on two floors. The build is of brick plastered walls and roof tiling. The house is 28 years old but it is in good condition. The estimated annual energy demand of the building for heating is 45,3 kWh/(m²year) and 69,9 kWh/(m²year) for cooling. The house has an energy efficiency rating of C according with the Cyprus Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) regulation. The building annual energy demand estimated for the reference envelop defined by the EPC regulation is 21,92 kWh/(m²year) for heating and 49,77 kWh/(m²year) for cooling.

SYSTEM LAYOUT

In Cyprus´s demosite, the system was designed as a set of PCM storage tanks coupled with a geothermal heat pump, flat solar collectors and low temperature indoor fan coils. The thermal energy storage PCM tanks stores energy at three different levels. The Cold storage tanks for residential space cooling, the Hot storage tanks for residential space heating and a TES tank to deliver DHW.

The solar loop is directly connected to the Hot PCM tanks and PCM storage tank for deliverable DWH. An electric water heater is installed in series after the PCM hot water tank as a backup for the production of hot water. The solar loop has a heat dissipater for safety reasons.

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